

1 Managing challenging waste fractions: Mechanical recycling of FFP3 2 masks and environmental assessment

3 Yasemin Celik*, Meret Jürgens, Niklas Rode, Madina Shamsuyeva, Hans-Josef Endres

4 *IKK - Institute of Plastics and Circular Economy, Leibniz Universität Hannover, An der Universität 2, 30823 Garbsen,*
5 *Germany*

6 *Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* celik@ikk.uni-hannover.de

7 **Article type**

8 Note

9 **ORCID IDs**

10 Yasemin Celik (0000-0003-3104-0868), Meret Jürgens (0009-0006-0593-0030), Niklas Rode (0009-0007-7985-2757),
11 Madina Shamsuyeva (0000-0003-2564-4104), Hans-Josef Endres (0000-0001-8202-3190)

12 **Abstract**

13 Multi-material materials are challenging waste fractions for mechanical recycling processes. One example of these
14 waste streams are expired but unused Filtering Face Piece (FFP) masks that are commonly disposed of through
15 incineration, despite being biologically uncontaminated. This study investigates the technical feasibility and
16 environmental performance of mechanically recycling FFP3 masks. A mechanical recycling approach was developed,
17 that consists of pre-shredding, shredding, pelletising and extrusion. The resulting polypropylene recycle was
18 compared to commercially available recycles based on the melt flow rate and mechanical properties: tensile strength,
19 tensile modulus and impact strength. The recycled material exhibits suitable melt flow rates and comparable or higher
20 mechanical properties. In addition, a life cycle assessment (LCA) was performed to compare the potential
21 environmental impacts of developed recycling approach with the current waste treatment, incineration with energy
22 recovery. While incineration shows lower net impacts due to energy credits, mechanical recycling can achieve net-
23 negative environmental impacts when the recycle substitutes virgin polypropylene in appropriate product
24 applications. The results demonstrate the technical and environmental potential of mechanically recycling expired
25 FFP3 masks, while highlighting limitations related to mask design variability, data availability for the environmental
26 assessment, and transferability to other mask types.

27 **Keywords**

28 recycling, FFP masks, life cycle assessment, multi-layer materials, plastic waste

29 1. Introduction

30 Currently, most post-consumer plastic recyclates come from packaging recycling, which is characterised by established
31 legal frameworks and mature collection and logistics systems. For other plastic waste streams, particularly from
32 technical and medical applications, there are currently few functioning circular solutions [1]. This waste is often
33 either used for energy recovery or sent to landfill, even though it contains significant amounts of valuable materials.
34 Historically, their material and product development focused on optimising processing and usage properties, while
35 recyclability and the use of recycled materials played only a minor role. However, a functioning circular economy
36 beyond the packaging sector is essential for the future-proof, resilient and sustainable use of plastics. In addition to
37 recycling-friendly design ('design for recycling'), this requires further development of mechanical recycling
38 technologies and targeted material and product design that enables the use of high-quality recyclates and multiple
39 recycling ('design for recyclates') [2]. At the same time, input streams from technical applications that have hardly been
40 used to date must be tapped and the quality of the resulting recyclates significantly improved.

41 During the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a significant increase in the manufacture of personal protective
42 equipment (PPE), with a particular emphasis on Filtering Face Piece (FFP) masks [3, 4]. This increase in production has
43 resulted in a corresponding rise in the amount of the PPE waste [5]. However, after the pandemic, PPE equipment still
44 produces a significant amount of plastic waste [6]. This includes both used end-of-life FFP masks and masks which
45 were not sold until the expiry date was reached. The expiry date primarily covers respirators that have been certified
46 in accordance with the European standard EN 149. FFP masks that have exceeded their expiry date should not be used
47 for protective purposes where certified respiratory protection is required, so they are disposed of. Due to the absence
48 of a comprehensive circular economy system for waste management, even unsold and clean (biologically
49 uncontaminated) FFP masks are subject to the conventional procedures for material disposal.

50 At the same time, the very lightweight FFP masks have not been considered as potential input for effective
51 recycling due to their complex material composition, including various plastics, adhesives and metals [7]. In particular,
52 so-called FFP3 masks, which are even more protective than FFP1 and FFP2 masks, consist primarily of polyolefin
53 nonwovens such as polypropylene (PP), in addition to components ensuring the mask's function, such as metal nose
54 clips with a polyvinyl chloride (PVC) nose pad, typically elastic bands, and an additional PP breathing valve [8]. In view
55 of growing environmental awareness, practical recycling approaches for waste streams like these are needed. There is
56 a lack of fundamental practical feasibility study on a small technical scale that examines the material-technical
57 mechanical recyclability of the expired FFP3 masks [9, 10]. Also, the actual environmental impacts are to be considered
58 when developing recycling approaches.

59 The aim of this work is to develop a complete process chain for the mechanical recycling of individually packaged
60 genuine expired FFP3 masks by separating foreign components, regranulating and testing material properties in
61 practical trials. The findings of this study evaluate the material-technical potential of FFP3 masks as a possible input
62 stream to produce high-quality plastic recyclates and identify the most important weak points that should be
63 addressed for successful transferability into practice. To ensure the overarching goal of more sustainable material
64 consumption and waste treatment strategies is met, the environmental impacts are also assessed.

63 2. Materials and Methods

64 The FFP3 masks used in this study are Xplore-1730+V masks from the Xplore series manufactured by Dräger Safety
65 AG & Co. KGaA (Germany). The trials were performed on 25 kg of individually packaged masks. Each mask consists of
66 several spunbond and meltblown nonwoven layers made of PP, as well as a PP valve, metal nose clip, PVC nose pad,
67 polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and elastane elastic band and other small parts such as fasteners (see Fig. 1).

68 2.1. Mechanical recycling

69 The masks were subjected to the following process steps, which are presented in Figure 2 and described in detail
70 below: pre-shredding, shredding, pelletising and extrusion. Injection moulding is used to produce test specimens. The
71 process route is a proof of concept, i.e. the individual process stages have been examined with regard to material
72 performance, but material losses, energy efficiency, etc. have not yet been optimised. The separation and shredding
73 of the PP, which is to be recycled in this study, from foreign components in FFP3 masks is one of the most important
74 steps in the pre-treatment and recycling process. Shredding of complete FFP3 masks produces a large amount of fluff
75 in which hard components such as metal clips and valves become entangled. Preliminary tests have shown that sorting
76 the fractions according to this approach does not allow for pure separation, neither by using wet chemical processes

77 nor by wind sifting (see Fig. 3). Therefore, for clear separation, the masks were first pre-cut along the edge with GUS
 78 12V-300 electric shears (Robert Bosch GmbH, Germany) so that the nose clip and elastic band could be separated.
 79 This step causes a small loss of PP nonwovens, but enables the remaining components, the PP valve and most PP
 80 nonwovens, to be sorted by type.

83
 84 Figure 1: Material fractions of different components in the tested mask type 'Xplore-1730+V', FEPM: fluor elastomer, MVQ: silicone
 85 elastomer

86
 87 Figure 2: Processes of the mechanical recycling approach

88
 89 Figure 3: Unsuccessful sorting fractions from a) wet chemical processes and b) wind sifting: no separation visible
 90

91 The subsequent shredding was carried out using a 25.38s cutting mill (Wanner Technik GmbH, Germany) with a
 92 screen size of 6 mm to ensure reproducible pre-treatment and particularly to reduce the disruptive behaviour of the
 93 hard PP components in the pelletising process. Hard plastic components that are too large can have a negative impact
 94 on the rest of the process. In this step, PP fractions of hard and soft components were produced.
 95 Due to the high proportion of fluff in the shredded material, direct dosing of the ground material into the extruder
 96 is not possible due to bridging. Therefore, the shredded material is usually agglomerated or pelletised before
 97 extrusion, where it is strongly compressed or compacted but not completely melted. For compaction, the material was
 98 pelletised using a Flat die pelleting press 14-175 (Amandus Kahl GmbH & Co. KG, Germany), using a die with a pressing
 99 ratio of 1:3 (hole diameter 4 mm, pressing stroke 12 mm) at an average speed of 1200 RPM. This reduced the fluff
 100 content, homogenised the material and produced defined bulk densities with a compression from 0.05 kg/l to 0.4 kg/l
 101 after pelletisation. The pellets produced were then extruded to granulate at typical PP process temperatures (180 °C)
 using a Process 16 laboratory extruder (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany). The extrusion was carried out under
 vacuum to remove

102 volatile components. The extruder is a twin-screw extruder with a screw diameter of 16 mm and an L/D ratio of 40:1.
 103 The melt flow rate (MFR) of the regranulate was determined according to DIN EN ISO 1133 using an extrusion
 104 plastometer MFR/MVR ZwickRoell Aflow (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) at 230 °C under 2.16 kg (MFR n=3).

105 2.2. Mechanical testing

106 Test specimens for mechanical testing according to the DIN EN ISO 527-1 (type CW) were produced from the
 107 regranulate in an injection moulding machine BOY XS (Dr. Boy GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Processing was carried out
 108 under the usual process parameters for PP (200 °C). The produced test specimens were then conditioned in accordance
 109 with ISO 291 at 23°C und 50 rH for 48 hours. Mechanical characterisation includes tensile testing based on DIN EN
 110 ISO 527-2 at room temperature using a ZwickRoell Z030 TEW material testing machine (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG,
 111 Germany). The impact strength test was determined in accordance with ISO 179-2 using a ZwickRoell HIT25P
 112 pendulum impact tester (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Multiple test specimens with type 1 according to ISO
 113 179-1 were tested for each. (Tensile strength n=8, Tensile modulus n=8, Impact strength n=10).

114 The characterisation results of the regranulate from the FFP3 masks were compared to commercially available PP
 115 recyclates for injection moulding application or thermoforming using information from the technical data sheets. The
 116 recyclates R1 to R3 used for comparison are listed in Table 1.

117 Table 1: Commercially available recyclates used for comparison during mechanical testing

Index	Name	Manufacturer	Data sheet
R1	Dipolen® PP	mtm plastics GmbH (Germany)	[8]
R2	Purpolen® PP	mtm plastics GmbH (Germany)	[9]
R3	recythen® PP 10	ALBA Recycling GmbH (Germany)	[10]

118 2.3. Environmental assessment

119 The environmental impacts were assessed by performing a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the developed recycling
 120 approach and the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. The system boundaries were defined
 121 using a 'cut-off' approach from the collected waste to the production of regranulate for injection moulding. For
 122 reference, the results of the recycling approach were compared to the impacts of virgin material production and the
 123 current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. As much data as possible was taken from lab-scale and
 124 semi-industrial scale plants and was complemented by literature data. Thereby, the process data for the developed
 125 mechanical recycling approach was obtained for all processes listed in Table 2. The life cycle inventories for the
 126 environmental assessment were prepared using the 'LCA For Experts' software (formerly known as 'GaBi', version
 127 10.9.1.17) and the Managed LCA Database (formerly known as 'GaBi database', version 2025.1). More information on
 128 the life cycle inventories and underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

129 Table 2: Processes modelled for the mechanical recycling approach; scale indication based on equipment throughput (semi-
 130 industrial = low end of industrial throughput)

Process	Equipment	Data source	Scale
Shredding (manual cutting tool)	GUS 12V-300 electric shears (Robert Bosch GmbH, Germany)	Estimated data	Lab
Shredding (cutting mill)	25.38s cutting mill (Wanner Technik GmbH, Germany)	Collected data	Lab
Pelletising	Flat die pelleting press 14-175 (Amandus Kahl GmbH & Co. KG, Germany)	Collected and Estimated data	Lab
Extrusion	Process 16 laboratory extruder (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany)	Collected data	Lab
Granulation	-	Dataset	Industrial

131 The environmental impacts were calculated using the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method provided by the
 132 European Commission. The results of the 16 assessed environmental impact categories that are covered by the EF 3.1
 133 method were summarized using a normalized and weighted single score with normalisation and weighting factors [11].

134 **3. Results and Discussion**

135 **3.1. Mechanical testing**

136 The PP recycled from FFP3 masks was examined in terms of its mechanical properties and compared with three
137 commercially available recyclates (R1–R3) (Figure 4). The MFR of the recycled granulate is significantly lower than that
138 of commercial recyclates. The MFR is an indirect indicator of the average molecular weight and chain length: a lower
139 MFR indicates higher viscosity and longer molecular chains. Considering that the regranulate has undergone multiple
140 thermal stresses, the reduced MFR may also be caused by cross-linked or partially oxidised polymer chains, which
141 restrict flowability. While such changes affect the processing properties, they also increase the stiffness and
142 dimensional stability of the material [12, 13]. For further processing of the recyclate in technical applications, the MFR
143 could be adapted to specific process conditions through targeted compounding or additive modification without
144 compromising mechanical integrity. The tensile tests show that the tensile strength of recycled PP is comparable to that
of commercial recyclates, while the tensile modulus is significantly higher. This indicates a stiffer, less deformable
material structure. At the molecular
level, this can be explained by a shortening of the polymer chains and a denser packing of the molecules, which
occurred during thermal stress and reprocessing. Shorter chains can crystallise more compactly, slightly increasing
crystallinity and raising the tensile modulus [14]. At the same time, this can lead to a certain reduction in stress in
amorphous areas, which supports energy absorption under impact loading [15]. The impact strength of the recycled
granulate exceeds that of commercial recyclates, indicating a homogeneous
structure without significant defects or agglomerations. Despite previous use in masks, the material exhibits good
mechanical energy absorption capacity, suggesting a balanced mixture of amorphous and crystalline areas. The
combination of higher tensile modulus and increased impact strength suggests that thermal processing has produced
a stabilising density of crystallite areas without resulting in brittle structures.
In summary, the regranulate from FFP3 masks exhibits mechanically robust and structurally stable properties
despite multiple thermal stressing.

160
161 Figure 4: Mechanical testing results for the regranulate from the FFP3 masks compared to commercially available recyclates (R1-
162 R3)

163 **3.2. Environmental assessment**

164 The mechanical recycling approach is compared to the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery
165 (see Fig. 5). Incineration has higher impacts, namely 627% of the recycling impacts, but receives credits (-573%) for
166 recovering electricity and heat. In general, it is expected that the credits for energy recovery are going to decrease in
167 the future, when more sustainable energy production processes are substituted. However, currently, incineration has
168 net impacts of 54% of the recycling impacts after totalling the impacts and credits.

169

170 Figure 5: Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for mechanical recycling and incineration with energy recovery of 1 kg of
 171 waste FFP3 masks (100%: mechanical recycling impacts) *material credit only applicable with appropriate product application
 172

173 On the other hand, the recycling of 1 kg of waste FFP3 masks produces 534 g of recyclate. An environmental credit
 174 can be achieved when the recyclate can substitute the same amount of virgin material in a product application similar
 175 to the energy credits. In that case, the material credit for avoiding virgin PP production (-1042%) leads to net-negative
 176 environmental impacts for the mechanical recycling approach (-942%) that are much lower than the net impacts of
 177 the incineration process.

178 **3.3. Limitations**

179 Several limitations must be considered. The transferability of the process is restricted due to the highly
 180 individualised design of FFP3 masks, including complex layer structures, multi-material components, and integrated
 181 elements such as metal clips, elastic bands, and valves. Prior to recycling, post-consumer masks require thorough
 182 cleaning and disinfection to ensure material homogeneity and compliance with hygiene regulations. The lack of
 183 dedicated collection infrastructure further complicates practical implementation, although energy recovery may
 184 provide a more feasible alternative in certain cases [16].

185 Regarding the environmental impacts, in this study, the mechanical properties of the recycled material were only
 186 compared to other recyclates. Therefore, without a product application, no statements on the substitution potential
 187 for virgin PP and therefore the actual environmental benefits are possible. However, since the recyclates are
 188 commercially available, the authors assume a market demand for them. Also, the LCA results were calculated from a
 189 mix of available lab-scale and semi-industrial scale data and literature data. Therefore, they represent the status quo
 190 of the recycling approach. Future implementation on a larger scale may result in different results due to an increased
 191 efficiency or different configurations of the modelled processes.

192 **4. Conclusions**

193 The study shows that recycling safety-critical products such as FFP3 masks is not only sustainable, but can also
 194 provide high-quality materials for technical applications. The developed recycling approach is technically feasible,
 195 process-stable and shows potential for industrial upscaling. The process steps (shredding, pelletising, extrusion and
 196 injection moulding of the regranulate) were carried out without complications and resulted in a regranulate with
 197 appropriate mechanical properties: A low MFR indicates higher viscosity, longer chains or partial cross-linking and
 198 thus lower flowability. A high tensile modulus means denser molecular packing and increased crystallinity, resulting in
 199 increased stiffness. High impact strength suggests a homogeneous structure with associated improved energy
 200 absorption.

201 The environmental assessment indicates environmental benefits compared to the current waste treatment,
 202 incineration with energy recovery, provided that an appropriate product application of the recyclate is available. When
 203 the regranulate can be substitute virgin PP, the overall environmental impacts might improve significantly compared
 204 to the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. However, due to the exploratory nature of the
 205 material processing, the data basis for the life cycle assessment is limited. Future work should investigate the
 transferability of the presented recycling process to other mask types and complex multi-component products. In
 particular, the development of standardised pre-treatment and cleaning processes for post-consumer recyclates
 could further improve homogeneity and process stability. This would also improve the data basis for further
 environmental assessments.

Supplementary Information

Yasemin Celik*, Meret Jürgens, Niklas Rode, Madina Shamsuyeva, Hans-Josef Endres

Institute of Plastics and Circular Economy, Leibniz Universität Hannover, An der Universität 2, 30823 Garbsen, Germany

* Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* celik@ikk.uni-hannover.de

A. Mechanical recycling

For reference to the description of the mechanical recycling approach, the decomposed FFP3 mask is shown in Figure 206.1.

Figure 206.1: Deconstructed FFP 3 mask Xplore-1730+V by Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA (Germany)

B. Life Cycle Inventory

The life cycle inventories are listed in Table 206.1 to Table 206.5. The following general assumptions were applied:

- Electricity is supplied by the general German electricity mix (2022). Process water supply is modelled as tap water from groundwater.
- Residual waste is treated as commercial waste. For plastic residues, the process 'DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery. For all other residues, the process 'DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery.
- No primary data was available for granulation of the extrudate. Therefore, a generic dataset was used to account for these processes.
- Transport processes were not considered, as it was assumed that all recycling processes would be combined at the same location.
- Virgin PP material for reference as modelled using the 'DE: Polypropylene granulate (PP) mix' process.
- For the alternative disposal route, it was assumed that the waste stream would usually be incinerated in Germany with energy recovery. This was modelled using the same processes as the ones used for the residual waste including credits for energy recovery. It was assumed that the masks consist of 75 wt.% plastic and 25 wt.% other materials (commercial waste).

Table 206.1: Life cycle inventory for the shredding (manual cutting tool)

Shredding (manual cutting tool)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Waste stream (masks)	1.00	kg	No burdens (cut-off)	–
Electricity	0.036	kWh	Estimate based on battery capacity	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Masks (shredded)	0.75	kg	–	–
Residual waste	0.25	kg	Commercial waste (metals, rubber, other residues)	DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H ₂ O content)

Table 206.2: Life cycle inventory for the shredding (universal cutting mill)

Shredding (cutting mill)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Masks (shredded)	3.00	kg	–	–
Electricity	0.21	kWh	–	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
PP material	2.70	kg	–	–
Residual waste	0.30	kg	Commercial waste (plastics)	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H2O content)

Table 206.3: Life cycle inventory for the pelletising

Pelletising				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
PP material	4.00	kg	–	–
Electricity	0.04	kWh	Estimate based on previous runs and measurements	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Water	0.20	kg		DE: Tap water from groundwater
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Pellets	3.70	kg	–	–
Residual waste	0.30	kg	–	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H2O content)
Water (evaporated)	0.20	kg	Assumption	Water emissions to air

Table 206.4: Life cycle inventory for the extrusion

Extrusion				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Pellets	1.00	kg	–	–
Electricity	0.27	kWh	–	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Extrudate	0.90	kg	–	–
Filter residue	0.10	kg	Commercial waste (plastics)	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H2O content)

Table 206.5: Life cycle inventory for the granulation

Granulation				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Extrudate	1.00	kg	–	–
Granulation	1.00	kg	No primary data	DE: Granulator (30-1500 kg/h throughput)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Regranulate	1.00	kg	–	–

C. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The results of the life cycle impact assessment are listed in Table 206.6. The normalized and weighted Single Score results are presented alongside the individual impact category results. The results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%) for data confidentiality reasons.

Table 206.6: Results of the life cycle impact assessment for the respective reference flow; for data confidentiality reasons, all results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Recycling approach	Material credit for substitution of virgin PP (negative)	Incineration	Energy credit for substitution energy production (negative)
Reference flow		1 kg of FFP3 masks	mass of produced recycle	1 kg of FFP3 masks	amount of produced energy
Acidification	mol H+ eq	100%	-1084%	470%	-842%
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	100%	-291%	483%	-252%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	100%	8355%	-81%	978%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	100%	2525%	-137%	2758%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	100%	-787%	462%	-840%
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	100%	-538%	425%	-597%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	100%	82015%	-4653%	29507%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	100%	-3259%	571%	-2018%
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	100%	-1265%	120%	-3382%
Land Use	pt	100%	138%	-21%	740%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	100%	-1205%	115%	-3368%
Particulate matter	disease incidences	100%	-1926%	568%	-1335%
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	100%	-1567%	510%	-885%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	100%	1752%	-30%	629%
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	100%	6995%	-238%	6149%
Water use	m3 world eq	100%	-20%	259%	-14%
Single Score	-	100%	-1042%	627%	-573%

The normalised results (in %) for material and energy credit are positive in some impact categories, which may seem counterintuitive at first glance. This is because the developed recycling approach generates waste that is incinerated. The energy produced during this incineration is credited when modelling the recycling approach. In some impact categories, this credit is higher than the impacts for energy and water consumed by the recycling approach. As a result, the numerical results for the recycling approach, which are used as a reference (as '100%'), are negative in some impact categories. Since the numerical results for material and energy credit are also negative (i.e. the same negative sign as for the recycling approach), the normalised results (in %) become positive in these impact categories, even though a credit is represented.

207

208

209

210 Author contributions

211 Yasemin Celik: Project administration, Conceptualization, Writing–original draft, Investigation. Meret Jürgens:
 212 Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing–original draft, Niklas Rode: Project administration, Investigation.
 213 Madina Shamsuyeva: Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. Hans-Josef Endres: Funding
 214 acquisition, Supervision

215 Funding sources

216 This work was financially supported by the Ministry of Science and Culture (MWK) of Lower Saxony as a part of the
 217 grant number ZN 4173 for the project ReKon – Recycling concepts for high-quality mechanical recycling of previously
 218 non-recyclable waste streams of technical plastic components from the mobility, energy, electronic and electrical
 219 equipment (E&E) and health/pharmaceutical sectors.

220 **Conflicts of interest**

221 There are no conflicts to declare.

222 **Acknowledgements**

223 The authors acknowledge Dräger (Dräger Safety AG & Co. KGaA) for supplying the materials used in this study.

224 **Data availability**

225 The data supporting this article have been included as part of the Supplementary Information.

226 **References**

- 227 1. Lindner C, Arnold M, Hein J (2025) Status quo und Prognose des Bedarfs und der Verfügbarkeit von
228 Post-Consumer-Rezyklaten im Jahr 2030
- 229 2. van der Vegt M, Velzing E-J, Rietbergen M et al. (2022) Understanding Business Requirements for
230 Increasing the Uptake of Recycled Plastic: A Value Chain Perspective. *Recycling* 7.
231 <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling7040042>
- 232 3. Patrício Silva AL, Prata JC, Walker TR et al. (2021) Increased plastic pollution due to COVID-19
233 pandemic: Challenges and recommendations. *Chem Eng J* 405:126683.
234 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126683>
- 235 4. Shirvanimoghaddam K, Czech B, Yadav R et al. (2022) Facemask Global Challenges: The Case of
236 Effective Synthesis, Utilization, and Environmental Sustainability. *Sustainability* 14:737.
237 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020737>
- 238 5. Roberts KP, Phang SC, Williams JB et al. (2022) Increased personal protective equipment litter as a
239 result of COVID-19 measures. *Nat Sustain* 5:272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-021-00824-1>
- 240 6. Oliveira AM, Patrício Silva AL, Soares AMVM et al. (2023) Current knowledge on the presence,
241 biodegradation, and toxicity of discarded face masks in the environment. *J Environ Chem Eng*
242 11:109308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.109308>
- 243 7. Crespo C, Ibarz G, Sáenz C et al. (2021) Study of Recycling Potential of FFP2 Face Masks and
244 Characterization of the Plastic Mix-Material Obtained. A Way of Reducing Waste in Times of Covid-19.
245 *Waste Biomass Valorization* 12:6423–6432. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-021-01476-0>
- 246 8. Torres FG, De-la-Torre GE (2021) Face mask waste generation and management during the COVID-19
247 pandemic: An overview and the Peruvian case. *Science of The Total Environment* 786:147628.
248 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147628>
- 249 9. Milam-Guerrero J, Kwon D-J, Choi YY et al. (2023) From waste to wearable: an alternative waste stream
250 for unusable textiles turned into piezoelectric textiles. *RSC Sustainability* 1:326–334.
251 <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2SU00068G>
- 252 10. Zhang M, Sun S, Liu J et al. (2023) Recycling polypropylene from non-woven disposable masks in
253 developing a three-dimensional printing filament. *Textile Research Journal* 93:2789–2808.
254 <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175221147722>

- 255 11. Andreasi Bassi S, Biganzoli F, Ferrara N et al. (2023) Updated characterisation and normalisation factors
256 for the Environmental Footprint 3.1 method. JRC Technical Report, Luxembourg
- 257 12. Seifert L, Leuchtenberger-Engel L, Hopmann C (2024) Enhancing the Quality of Polypropylene
258 Recyclates: Predictive Modelling of the Melt Flow Rate and Shear Viscosity. *Polymers (Basel)* 16.
259 <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16162326>
- 260 13. Kissel WJ, Han JH, Meyer JA (2005) Polypropylene: Structure, Properties, Manufacturing Processes, and
261 Applications. In: Karian HG (ed) *Handbook of Polypropylene and Polypropylene Composites; Revised
262 and Expanded; second edition.* Marcel Dekker, Inc., Basel/New York, pp 11–35
- 263 14. Huang P-W, Peng H-S (2021) Number of Times Recycled and Its Effect on the Recyclability, Fluidity and
264 Tensile Properties of Polypropylene Injection Molded Parts. *Sustainability* 13:11085.
265 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131911085>
- 266 15. Ladhari A, Kucukpinar E, Stoll H et al. (2021) Comparison of Properties with Relevance for the
267 Automotive Sector in Mechanically Recycled and Virgin Polypropylene. *Recycling* 6:76.
268 <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling6040076>
- 269 16. Abhilash, Inamdar I (2022) Recycling of plastic wastes generated from COVID-19: A comprehensive
270 illustration of type and properties of plastics with remedial options. *Sci Total Environ* 838:155895.
271 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155895>

271 **Figures and Tables**

- 272 • Figure 1: Material fractions of different components in the tested mask type 'Xplore-1730+V', FEPM: fluor
273 elastomer, MVQ: silicone elastomer
- 274 • Figure 2: Processes of the mechanical recycling approach
- 275 • Figure 3: Unsuccessful sorting fractions from a) wet chemical processes and b) wind sifting: no separation visible
- 276 • Figure 4: Mechanical testing results for the regranulate from the FFP3 masks compared to commercially available
277 recyclates (R1-R3)
- 278 • Figure 5: Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for mechanical recycling and incineration with energy
279 recovery of 1 kg of waste FFP3 masks (100%: mechanical recycling impacts) *material credit only applicable with
280 appropriate product application
- 281
- 282 • Table 2: Commercially available recyclates used for comparison during mechanical testing
- 283 • Table 2: Processes modelled for the mechanical recycling approach; scale indication based on equipment
284 throughput (semi-industrial = low end of industrial throughput)